

Forecasting cryptocurrency markets through the use of time series models

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Abstract:

This paper analyses the efficiency of cryptocurrency markets by applying econometric models to different short-term investment horizons. A number of experiments are carried out to demonstrate that small training sets can still be used to build efficient and useful forecasts, which in turn can be transformed into straight-forward investment strategies. It also compares the application of selected models on cryptocurrency and mature stock markets. The forecasting accuracy of the models is explored using different error metrics and different horizons. The results suggest that the variation of the error estimates doesn't appear to be tightly related to the maturity of the markets, but rather depends on the intrinsic characteristics of the analyzed time series.

JEL Classifications: G17, C52, C53

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1. Introduction

Efficient market hypothesis (EMH) (Fama, 1970) implies that all available information is reflected in the asset prices one observes, thus adjusting for the taken risks it would not be feasible to implement a trading strategy that consistently generates returns in excess of the respective market index. A vast number of studies (Sanjiv, Mokashi, & Culkin, 2018; Cajueiro & Tabak, 2004; Xiaming, Haiyan, & Romilly, 1997; Kristoufek, 2018) have been devoted to testing for EMH presence and also to proving it right or wrong under different conditions. Yet the payoff of finding a way to predict stock markets in a way that would provide excessive returns is of great importance for both practitioners and academia. During the last decade there has been a steady growth in the body of literature focused on this matter with some papers reporting more than 80% accuracy in forecasting price direction change (de Oliveira, Nobre, & Zárate, 2013; Patel, Shah, Thakkar, & Kotecha, 2015; Lee, 2009). While it can be argued that temporary inefficiency does not rule out the EMH completely, the speed at which markets converge to their efficiency level is critical for benefiting from arbitrage opportunities. As rational investors take advantage of these opportunities the prices will again move to reflect all available information, though in reality, this would not necessarily happen immediately. Thus, the adjustment period is of vital importance because of the following reasons:

- Testing for market efficiency with different forecasting horizons may yield different results and eventually trigger wrong conclusions.

Market efficiency over very short time horizons has been analyzed in (Busse & Green, 2002) and (Kayal & Maheswaran, 2018). While there are purely technical limitations to the speed of transaction processing and information transfer, it is the responsiveness that gets more and more important as automated trading systems are used worldwide. Therefore, the selection of an appropriate investment horizon is a key factor for choosing between available forecasting methods and algorithms.

- Building investment strategies based on forecasting methods may result in different success rates.

In addition to the limitations built within forecasting models, different time horizons may also expose them to regime changes and major changes in the underlying processes. Evidence for regime switching in stock returns has been found in (Shen & Long, 2016; Constantinou, Georgiades, Kazandjian, & Kouretas, 2006; Schaller & Van Norden, 1997) which means that the accuracy of the studied algorithms (thus the profitability of the respective investment strategies) will depend on the frequency of switches, the length of the regimes and the exposure to them in the forecasted time period. In (Kang, Hyndman, & Smith-Miles, 2017) different models have been shown to give quite disparate results even when applied to the same time series but with different forecasting and training horizons.

In this paper, we study the effects of different investment forecasting horizons on the accuracy of ARIMA models, provided that the analyzed financial data inputs come from markets of different size, maturity and assets classes. We carry out a number of experiments to see how small training sets can still be used to build efficient and useful forecasts. Based on these results we analyze some straight-forward investment strategies and compare their payoffs when used in mature and highly liquid markets and when applied to cryptocurrency trading. There are multiple factors that influence the accuracy of forecasts, but within the context of this study we have limited them to the following groups:

- Characteristics and type of the time series being analyzed.

Characteristics and type of the time series refer to the presence of different regimes, seasonality, extreme values, jumps and clustering of volatility to name a few. It is beyond the scope of this paper to elaborate on all possibilities and we rely on stationarity tests and use of differences in the series.

- Accuracy measure employed in the analysis.

Accuracy measures have been discussed in details in (Makridakis, 1993; Fildes & Makridakis, 1995), yet for this study, it is of primary significance to be able to map each measure to an investment strategy goal. Therefore, we have decided to use three separate error metrics - mean absolute error (MAE), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and root mean squared error (RMSE).

- Length of the forecasting horizon.

The length of the forecasting horizon plays an important role in selecting appropriate valuation models and building investment strategies. Under imperfect conditions where the market participants are subjected to different constraints, it is possible to observe behaviour that deviates from the theoretically optimal one. For example, in (Benartzi & Thaler, 1995) the “myopic loss aversion” effect is analyzed with regard to premiums in returns of different asset classes. We analyze the importance of the investment and

forecasting horizon in an even more restricted environment - using the same investment vehicle and in a short period of time.

This study is organized as follows: Section 2 covers the methodology of the study and elaborates on the ARIMA model. The data used in the study is described in section 3. Section 4 describes the process of model selection, followed by the numerical results in section 5 and limitations in section 6. Finally, the analysis and the key conclusions are presented in section 7.

2. Methodology

Availability of computing power has facilitated the use of multiple statistical and simulation models in analyzing financial time series. It is beyond the scope of this paper to fully describe and classify different approaches. Making a comparison between available models and approaches is even harder when we consider the multiple error metrics that could be applied and the vast number of applications, where separate cases may have specific characteristics like multiple regimes, volatility clustering to name a few.

We focus on studying the application of ARIMA models in cryptocurrency analysis because of the following reasons:

- It is one of the most common approaches used as a reference when testing more complex models. While the popularity of ARIMA brings a lot of papers dedicated to extending and combining it with other methods (Babu & Reddy, 2014; Wang, Zhang, Qin, & Zhang, 2017), it also means that there are more frequent misuses of the approach with too many efforts put on estimating the optimal parameters of the respective instance and not too much attention on the importance of the investment horizon.
- A number of studies have shown that ARIMA is able to provide similar and sometimes even better accuracy compared to other machine learning methods (Makridakis, Spiliotis, & Assimakopoulos, 2018; Lee, Sehwan, & Jongdae, 2007). Yet ARIMA models are easier to explain in particular compared to deep learning alternatives.
- It is easier to combine ARIMA models with other methods aiming at specific characteristics of the analyzed data (like for example targeting volatility clustering with ARIMA and GARCH).

Assuming a time series of variable Y_{t_n} are available, we can model them as a linear combination of their previous values in time plus current and past values of a white-noise error term. Using y_{t_n} to denote the d -th difference of the original time series, in accordance with equation (1) and the lag operator, ARIMA can be summarized as in (2).

$$y_{t_n} = \begin{cases} Y_{t_n}, d = 0 \\ Y_{t_n} - Y_{t_{n-1}}, d = 1 \\ (Y_{t_n} - Y_{t_{n-1}}) - (Y_{t_{n-1}} - Y_{t_{n-2}}), d = 2 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Estimation of the parameters in equation (2) depends on the values of p , q and d , which are identified following Box-Jenkins method.

$$\left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i L^i\right) y_{t_n} = \left(1 + \sum_{j=1}^q \theta_j L^j\right) \varepsilon_{t_n} \quad (2)$$

The algorithm used to choose and test a model consists of five different steps:

- 1) Selecting the order of differencing (d), based on stationarity tests with ADF.
- 2) Selecting boundary values for autoregressive and MA order that are based on ACF and PACF decay.
- 3) Model selection based on AIC in the available p and q space (with d estimated at step 1).
- 4) Define set of forecast horizons to check, depending on the assessed investment strategies and preferences.
- 5) Calculate error metrics (MAE, MAPE and RMSE) with the selected ARIMA model over the specified forecast horizons and assess the performance of the selected model.

Using hourly data over a horizon of one year it is possible to build a sufficiently large sample size, which reduces the risk of overfitting and selecting that largest available model with AIC (Burbine, Fryer, & Sturtevant, 2015; Koehler & Murphree, 1988).

In order to account for the special characteristics of cryptocurrency markets, we have also done a comparison of the selected model errors against well-established and highly liquid markets - using Dow Jones Industrial Average hourly time series as a reference. Cryptocurrency markets have a number of special characteristics that are of great importance to investors - and these go beyond the technical difficulties and reliability of the exchanges. The limited possibility for risk diversification means that market participants will have a restricted set of different coins to put their funds to. However, these coins can be highly correlated which also undermines the effect of diversification. In order to take into account the liquidity and cross-currency relations, we have included in our analysis time series representing both established coins and relatively new/small ones.

Lack of regulation and high market volatility are also two of the specific problems that cryptocurrency markets have been struggling with. Taking into account market reviewers in (Satis Group Crypto Research, 2018) have identified that a bit over 80% of all the projects in past years have been identified as a scam, the choices that market participants face are even more restricted than it seems at first glance. High volatility and volatility clustering are yet another property of cryptocurrency markets. While changes in volatility would require an extension (typically combining GARCH with ARIMA) of the model applied in this paper, we have decided to assess the accuracy of standard ARIMA, taking into account that forecast periods are relatively short which would limit (though not eliminate) the effects of clustering.

3. Market data used

For better coverage of different asset classes, we study some well-established instruments with new and vastly unregulated commodities like cryptocurrencies. Out of all available instruments we select five different investment vehicles. A major criterion for this selection is to include markets that differ in their growth and liquidity. Having a variety of instruments makes it possible to test ARIMA accuracy under different market conditions and with time series that have distinct intrinsic characteristics.

This study covers a period of one year (starting from 01.01.2018 till 31.12.2018) with intraday trading data as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. FINANCIAL TIME SERIES USED IN THE STUDY

INSTRUMENT	TICKS
1) DJIA It indicates the value of 30 large companies based in United States. DJIA is a price-weighted measure of 30 U.S. large companies. The index covers all industries except transportation and utilities (S&P Dow Jones Indices, n.d.).	1995
2) FTSE It covers the 100 companies with highest market capitalization on London stock exchange.	2269
3) ETH A token that serves the Ethereum platform. ETH is the second largest cryptocurrency by market capitalization. Its capitalization is valued at over USD 18B as of the end of April 2019 ^a .	8755
4) NEO A cryptocurrency that was founded in 2014 ^b . It is ranked 18-th cryptocurrency by market capitalization.	8752
5) HST A relatively new cryptocurrency. Its initial coin offering was on 13.11.2017 and it is ranked on 551-th place by market capitalization	8590

Source: Author.

Note: This is the data that is used in the study. ^a www.coinmarketcap.com. ^b www.neo.org

In order to minimize the impact of exchange rates, all cryptocurrency prices in the analysis are expressed in Bitcoins (BTC). This has been done due to the popularity of BTC and its de-facto role as fundamental cryptocurrency used for trading with other coins. Intraday trade information and quotations in OHLC format have been obtained from Finam (www.finam.ru) and Kucoin (www.kucoin.com) and special care has been taken to preprocess and remove missing values. With hourly data, this leaves between 1995 and 8590 observations for the selected period, as shown in Table 1. The major source for these variations in the available data is due to the non-continuous trading and working hours on the different exchanges.

4. Model selection

We test ARIMA models with data divided into eleven time intervals, representing short-term investment horizons. Data in the first interval is used to select model parameters and choose the particular model used to forecast time series. The next ten intervals are used in the process of forecasting and making decisions for trading actions - therefore the number of observations in Table 2 for intervals 1 till 9 is the same.

Different ARIMA models are used for one step ahead forecasting of the respective time series values. To select the most appropriate combination of p , q and d parameters we rely on Akaike Information Criteria (AIC). Table 2 highlights the best fitting parameters for selected horizons and time series, where initial limitation has been set that all values should be between 0 and 4. At the end of each period, the calibration procedure is repeated in order to confirm if there is a change in the time series behaviour and characteristics.

TABLE 2. ARIMA MODEL SELECTION

HORIZON / INTERVALS		DJIA	FTSE	ETH	NEO	HST
1	N	182	207	796	796	781
	p	2	3	2	2	3
	d	1	1	1	1	1
	q	0	2	3	3	3
2	p	3	2	2	2	3
	d	2	1	1	1	1
	q	1	1	2	2	3
3	p	2	0	1	1	3
	d	1	1	1	1	1
	q	2	1	0	0	3
4	p	3	1	1	3	3
	d	1	1	1	1	1
	q	3	0	0	3	3
5	p	1	2	3	1	2
	d	1	1	1	1	1
	q	0	2	0	1	1
6	p	1	3	2	0	3
	d	1	1	1	1	1
	q	0	1	0	1	3
7	p	2	2	1	0	0
	d	1	1	1	1	1
	q	2	2	1	1	1
8	p	1	1	0	3	1
	d	1	1	1	1	1
	q	0	0	2	0	2
9	p	3	2	1	3	1
	d	1	1	1	1	1
	q	0	2	0	2	1
10	N	177	199	795	792	780
	p	0	3	0	3	3
	d	1	1	1	1	1
	q	3	3	2	3	3

Source: Author.

Note: These are the p, d, q parameter estimations for the ARIMA model.

The forecasting process for DJIA is summarized on Figure 1 and consists of five steps repeated for every horizon.

FIGURE 1. DESCRIPTION OF DJI FORECASTING PROCEDURE

Source: Own elaboration.

Note: This is snapshot of the forecasting procedure.

The steps followed to forecast time series values are:

- 1) A selection of the best “p”, “d” and “q” parameters is done, using all the inputs available so far. After selecting the best fitting model, a forecast for the current period is initiated.
- 2) At first, a forecasted value is calculated for the first data point of the current investment period.
- 3) Then the first data point from the initial interval is excluded and the first point from the respective horizon is added to the input data.
- 4) The input data set from step (3) is used to forecasting the next value. Thus, data that is used by the ARIMA model, forms a sliding window with length equal to the length of the period.
- 5) After the last forecast for the current period, model selection procedure at step 1) is performed again to estimate new “p”, “d” and “q” parameters.

In light of market efficiency and predictability of the cryptocurrency markets, we expect to have limited ability to forecast prices and build simple trading strategies that consistently outperform the respective market. Taking into account that analyzed time period is short and emphasis is put on intraday trading and short-time investment horizons we can also draw conclusions by comparing our results for well-developed stock markets and cryptocurrencies. It is possible to extend the analysis with more complex trading strategies and use stochastic processes for modelling the changes in the time series (Milev, Georgieva, & Markovska, 2013). However, this is beyond the scope of this particular paper and subject to further study.

5. Numerical results

To account for different dynamics on the stock and currency markets we compare the performance of our ARIMA forecasts using error values. Therefore, after obtaining the forecasts for every horizon, we calculate MAPE, MAE and RMSE values. Figure 2 reveals

the changes of MAPE over the analyzed time periods for all instruments. Error values for DJI and FTSE are used as a reference when studying cryptocurrencies behaviour.

In addition, every time series shows a straight line marking the value of MAPE that is calculated with all available information - thus treating all 10 periods as one, without splitting the inputs.

FIGURE 2. MAPE CHANGES OVER ANALYZED INVESTMENT PERIODS

Source: Own elaboration.

Note: Plots of the MAPE estimates.

All of the individual horizons are characterized by significant variance in error values. MAPE for stock market forecasts follows a different pattern compared to cryptocurrencies.

For both DJI and FTSE time series we can see that there are consecutive periods in which MAPE remains below the whole sample value. It is either consistently declining (as in the case of DJI for periods 3 to 7) or changes but remains below the straight line (as in the case of FTSE). In contrast, MAPE for cryptocurrency time series varies around the whole sample value (with direction change of at least 5 times). This is in part due to the fact that cryptocurrency markets are much more volatile and the volatility varies over time (Chu, Chan, Nadarajah, & Osterrieder, 2017; Catania & Grassi, 2017), which cannot be accounted for by ARIMA models used. On the other hand, this indicates that simple trading strategies will not succeed in crypto markets even if they aim at less developed and less liquid coins as HST in this sample case.

Table 3 provides a summary of MAPE, MAE and RMSE estimates and some of their key characteristics. While standard deviation of the respective error metrics can be useful to study their behaviour for very simple trading strategies as those studied here a ratio of the maximum and minimum value is easier to interpret. We focus on this metric because it shows how much different the result would be if we have chosen to test ARIMA only on the horizon with maximal MAPE instead of the horizon with minimal MAPE.

TABLE 3. ARIMA ERROR VALUES

INSTRUMENTS		DJI	FTSE	ETH	NEO	HST
Mean	MAPE	0.002542	0.001906	0.003953	0.016784	0.006036
	MAE	62.768065	13.870233	0.000223	0.000036	1.22E-06
	RMSE	91.030910	20.145619	0.000330	0.000051	1.81E-06
StdDev	MAPE	0.001137	0.000539	0.000750	0.004821	0.001429
	MAE	26.983183	3.490714	0.000106	0.00003	1.14E-06
	RMSE	35.317877	6.212371	0.000139	0.000045	1.74E-06
Min	MAPE	0.001039	0.001178	0.002942	0.008878	0.003670
	MAE	27.110992	8.760159	0.000092	0.00001	1.61E-07
	RMSE	43.562850	11.202597	0.000154	0.000015	2.49E-07
Max	MAPE	0.004364	0.002985	0.004843	0.025716	0.008520
	MAE	104.04085	20.981058	0.000432	0.000108	3.84E-06
	RMSE	148.29230	32.965854	0.000608	0.00016	5.88E-06
Whole period est.	MAPE	0.002623	0.001777	0.003901	0.006003	0.016461
	MAE	64.776983	13.031796	0.000212	0.000034	1.18E-06
	RMSE	99.648771	19.225030	0.000337	6.29E-05	2.44E-06
Max/Min	MAPE	4.2	2.53	1.65	2.9	2.32
	MAE	3.84	2.4	4.7	10.8	23.88
	RMSE	3.4	2.94	3.95	10.67	23.63

Source: Author.

Note: This is information and statistics of the error metrics.

There is a significant variance of the Max/Min ratio across different time series. For MAPE error it is between 4.2 and 1.65, while for RMSE and MAE the maximum value is 23.88 and 23.64 respectively. Since the last two columns refer to cryptocurrencies that are relatively new one would expect that the Max/Min ratio will be the largest for these two instruments. However, this applies only when referring to MAE and RMSE but does not hold for MAPE measure. The highest MAPE ratio is for DJI (4.2) which represents the most mature markets. At the same time, the MAPE lowest ratio is for ETH (1.65) which represents the most mature cryptocurrency market (compared to NEO and HST in our sample).

Our results indicate that in addition error measures used, the accuracy of forecasts (thus the expected payoff from simple trading strategies based on them) depends on the forecasting horizon and the amount of data used for calibrating the model. While it is expected that for really short-term trading, the expansion of the inputs will not benefit the users as they focus on capturing the current changes mainly, the difference in the accuracy is large enough to be taken into account when planning investments. It also needs to be taken into account for studies comparing the accuracy of different models as choosing a specific horizon may result in different conclusions.

6. Research limitations

The main limitations of the study arise from the data that is used. Firstly, the period of 1 year is not always sufficient for placing general conclusions. Covering longer periods could be beneficial, because the time series will reflect different regime changes. Secondly, there are two general asset classes examined in the study. Adding futures, options, forex, etc. could reveal a different behaviour of the error metrics.

7. Conclusions

ARIMA models are often used in comparison studies (Wang, Song, & Li, 2018; Khashei & Bijari, 2011) reporting the superiority of hybrid advanced models. However, the difference in the error measures (especially MAPE) is often not analyzed with regard to different forecasting horizons. We have demonstrated that there is a considerable difference in MAPE for the models aiming at different investment and forecasting periods. Since ARIMA models can produce forecasts with a significant difference in errors, depending on the horizon chosen and the input window length, this needs to be taken into account when comparing them with other analytical approaches. Study on cryptocurrency and stock markets shows that the error measured for the whole period, and for individual horizons tends to differ a lot and this effect is present in both mature and new markets and assets. For example, the ratio between the minimal MAPE and the global (whole period est.) MAPE for DJIA is more than 2.5. Our findings are in line with (Shynkevich, McGinnity, Coleman, Belatreche, & Li, 2017), where different window sizes and time horizons are used. While it is possible to average the forecasting results over different windows, for practical use this is not a viable approach as market participants would like to get the most accurate results corresponding to their own investment horizon and plan.

The key finding of the study is that the variation of the error estimates doesn't appear to be tightly related to the maturity of the markets, but rather depends on the intrinsic characteristics of the analyzed time series.

Over the last decade, a lot of efforts both from practitioners and academia (Hsu, Lessmann, Sung, Ma, & Johnson, 2016), have been devoted to creating trading strategies. The efficiency of these strategies mainly depends on the underlying predictive power of the models that are used. This study implies that choosing the right model should not be the only concern, but the variation of the model prediction accuracy should be taken into account.

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